

Protocol for the intercomparison of national CH₄ emissions estimated by inverse modelling systems for Western Europe – Phase 1

- version November 2021 -

L. Florentie, S. Houweling

1. Goal

This CH₄ inversion intercomparison effort aims at assessing the constraints of atmospheric measurements on national methane fluxes, in particular the long-term trend in those emissions. The main focus of this intercomparison is on national CH₄ emission estimates in (Western) Europe (including separation into anthropogenic and natural emissions) and their uncertainties, as well as the added value of satellite-based XCH₄ observations in this respect. In addition, we aim to formulate benchmarking procedures and best practices for inversion-based emission estimates.

We will perform sensitivity experiments to search for answers to the following questions:

- What is the uncertainty range of inversion-optimized national CH₄ emissions? Is this as expected given the uncertainties of input datasets, observations, transport models and the findings in other research efforts (e.g. previous intercomparison efforts and the work done in other CoCO₂ work packages)?
- How does the uncertainty in the absolute emissions compare to that of year-to-year changes and the long-term trend? Are inversions capable of robustly resolving changes in national emissions on the time-scale relevant for the global stock take?
- What validation measurements and benchmarking metrics are needed to quantify the performance of different inversion systems?
- Can we formulate guidelines and best practices for atmospheric inversion setups that are general enough to be used by non-scientific parties, and that will yield consistent results w.r.t. national CH₄ emission estimates?
- What is the readiness level of inversion systems for use of the CO₂M (which includes XCH₄ observations) in refining CH₄ emission reporting?

The desired outcome of this intercomparison consists of a top-down assessment of trends in national methane emissions and their consistency with bottom-up reporting. This includes the formulation of a set of benchmarking methodologies, performance metrics, and best-practices for regional emission inversions.

2. Relation to the VERIFY CH₄ inversion intercomparison

The current effort is closely linked to the experiment performed in work package 4 of the VERIFY project. Both efforts investigate the ability of regional inversion frameworks to

estimate CH₄ fluxes in Europe. However, this experiment extends the effort of the VERIFY project in the sense that

- (i) we are particularly interested in national emission estimates, and the role of atmospheric inversions for verification of those estimates,
- (ii) we will conduct a 2-stage assessment: the first stage focusses on the use of ICOS surface data, whereas the 2nd stage extends this with the use of satellite observations. Moreover, phase 2 will be used to test findings/guidelines from the first round of inversions.
- (iii) this assessment continues beyond the end of the VERIFY project, allowing us to study more recent years in the 2nd phase. This facilitates a better assessment of satellite-based inversions, but also lets us prepare for and eventually include the first global stock take.
- (iv) we explicitly welcome participation from groups not involved in the VERIFY project to increase the size of the ensemble of models and inversion methods.

To minimize the effort for research groups, this experiment starts from the same basis as the VERIFY intercomparison. This implies that inversions performed to participate in the VERIFY intercomparison will automatically satisfy the requirements for participation in the first phase of this experiment as well, although some additional output is requested to allow for the specific analyses that we intend to perform for the current study.

The specifications for this first phase can be found in the current protocol document, which is based largely on the VERIFY protocol. We therefore gratefully acknowledge the large effort done by the VERIFY team to set up this protocol, to gather and produce input datasets, and to harmonize the observation datasets.

3. Overview of the experiment

An important aim of this study consists of the definition of a benchmarking strategy to assess the performance of different emission estimates, and the formulation of best practices to define country emission totals. This study will therefore consist of 2 modelling & analysis phases:

- **Modelling phase 1:** National emission estimates based on atmospheric CH₄ inversions using surface measurements, according to the protocol described in this document.
- **Analysis phase 1:** Assessment of the submitted results, with focus on uncertainty reduction due to the observational constraints, the detection of long-term trends, and the impact of the performance of the atmospheric transport model. This phase will result in an updated benchmarking strategy and formulation of a first version of best practices (in consultation with the modelling groups).
- **Modelling phase 2:** New round of inversions according to an updated protocol (based on the outcome of phase 1). In this round the inversions will at least be extended (we aim for 2021). It includes the possibility to rerun the full period for those groups that wish to make changes to their setup, according to the new protocol. In this round we will also strongly encourage (new) submissions based on satellite-based XCH₄ observations.

- **Analysis phase 2:** This analysis round will strongly focus on the added observational constraint due to the availability of satellite observations. Moreover, the preliminary findings and best practices as resulting from phase 1 are tested. The desired outcome of this phase consists of the formulation of a set of benchmarking methodologies, performance metrics and best-practices for national CH₄ inversion-based emission estimates. Our findings will be written down in a technical report and a scientific publication.

We strongly encourage groups that participate in modelling phase 1 to also participate in modelling phase 2, for consistency of the analysis phases. New submissions for modelling phase 2 only are welcomed as well.

4. Timeline

When?	What?
Nov., 2021	Distribution of intercomparison protocol and input datasets for phase 1 to the modelling community
March 1, 2022	Deadline for submission of inversion results for phase 1 (<= 2018)
April, 2022	Discussion with the modelling groups about the results of phase 1
Oct., 2022	Distribution of intercomparison protocol and input datasets for phase 2 to the modelling community
April 1, 2023	Deadline for submission of inversion results for phase 2 (<= 2021)
June, 2023	Discussion with the modelling groups about the results of phase 2

5. Domain definition (spatial & temporal)

The regional inversions should cover at least the area from 15W to 35E and 35N to 70N. Modelers are free to choose the spatial resolution they deem most appropriate. National emission totals are to be provided for at least the EU27 countries and the UK.

The inversions should cover as many years as possible in the range 2005-2018. If it is not possible to provide results for the full period it is preferred if groups submit results for a selection of (separate) years, chosen such as to cover the full period as good as possible, and including at least the years 2008, 2013 and 2018. This way we can still study the trend in emissions.

6. Input Data

6.1 Prior CH₄ fluxes

An overview of the prior total CH₄ fluxes that we expect modelling groups to use for this experiment is given below in Table 1. This is the same dataset as used for the VERIFY experiment. The fluxes area available on our Research Drive, both on monthly 0.25°x 0.25°

Table 1: Prior CH₄ fluxes

Category	Data source	Original Resolution		Time period
Peatlands, Mineral soils (emissions & uptake), inundated	JSBACH-HIMMELI ¹	0.1°x 0.1°	daily	2005-2020
Inland water ²	ULB	0.1°x 0.1°	monthly	Climatology
Termites	Saunois, 2020	-	annually	Climatology
Ocean	Weber, 2021	0.25°x 0.25°	monthly	Climatology
Geological	Etiopo, 2015	-	annually	Climatology
Fossil fuels	EDGAR v6.0	0.1°x 0.1°	monthly	2005-2018
Agriculture and waste	EDGAR v6.0	0.1°x 0.1°	monthly	2005-2018
Biofuels & biomass burning	GFED-4.1s	0.25°x 0.25°	monthly	2005-2020

¹Covers Europe from 10.5°W to 33°E and 34.5°N to 73.5°N

²Covers Eurasia from 26°W to 55°E and 34°N to 78°N

resolution and in their original resolution, such that you can choose to use the resolution most suitable for your system. If you want to make use of the original flux dataset, please make sure that the total flux is conserved upon regridding. Note that fluxes for peatlands, mineral soils and inland water (lakes) are only given for a limited domain. If groups want to include fluxes for these categories *outside* the provided domain as well, they are free to use the fluxes there that they deem appropriate.

Modelling groups are free to decide whether or not to explicitly model the atmospheric OH sink (as its influence is expected to be very small over Europe). For groups that do wish to include it, please use the OH field provided on our Research Drive. Modelling groups that decide to submit an extra inversion (apart from the proposed experiments, see section 6.5), which makes use of isotope data, we strongly advise to include the atmospheric OH sink.

6.2 Atmospheric observations

As part of the VERIFY experiment a harmonized set of atmospheric observations of CH₄ mixing ratios was created. This set contains observations provided from the InGOS project (2005-2016), from NOAA flask sampling sites in Europe (2005-2018), from AGAGE, and additional data from European sites (ICOS, WDCGG and personal communications). The full site list is available with the input data. The list contains a label for each site to indicate whether it may be assimilated (thereby also distinguishing between a set of 'core' and 'other' observation sites, see section 6.5) or must be kept for validation purpose.

We request groups to submit at least an inversion using daytime (12:00 to 16:00 local time) surface observations only. As an additional submission, groups are free to use (satellite-based) observations in addition to or instead of the provided observations dataset. In that case, please clearly document the assimilated observations.

For mountain site observations (indicated in the observation dataset overview), we ask to only assimilate nighttime observations (0:00 to 6:00 local time), sampled at the real altitude. If groups wish to submit an additional inversion that also assimilates daytime observations, please use a sampling height in the middle between the model topography and the real altitude.

6.3 Boundary conditions

For consistency in the regional contribution, we require modelling groups that perform a regional inversion to use the CAMS v19r1 reanalysis data as background/boundary conditions. This data is based on assimilated surface observations only and can be downloaded from the Copernicus atmospheric data store:

<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-global-greenhouse-gas-inversion?tab=overview>

For groups that have a system which makes use of the Rödenbeck 2-step inversion approach [3], consistent baseline fluxes are available on our Research Drive.

6.4 Uncertainties

All assumed uncertainties and covariance structures must be documented well. To facilitate a meaningful comparison, please adhere to the following:

- Use the observational uncertainties as provided with the observed value for the surface observations. Note that some observations are reported without uncertainties. Uncertainties to be used in those cases can be found in the header of the particular file.
- On top of the observational uncertainty a model uncertainty should be included as deemed appropriate by the modelling groups. Please document the choice made.
- Uncertainties for the prior anthropogenic and natural fluxes are free to be chosen by the modelers, but should be in reasonable agreement with the current scientific consensus. So please support your choice by appropriate references. Useful sources may include Solazzo et al. 2021, Saunio et al. 2020, and Petrescu et al. 2020

6.5 Inversion experiments

We request modelling groups to submit inversion results for at least the baseline configuration, and we highly encourage submission of additional results for the experiments described below:

- **Baseline** (mandatory): assimilating the 'core' observations only, using each model's best set-up, but adhering to the requirements outlined in sections 6.1 to 6.4 of this protocol. Please submit results for as many years as possible within the range 2005-2020, but including at least 2008, 2013 and 2018.
- **Experiment 1**: Similar to the baseline inversion, but assimilating the 'other' observations in addition to the 'core' observations.

- **Experiment 2:** Similar to the baseline inversion, but doubling the relative uncertainty of the anthropogenic prior fluxes compared to the natural fluxes,
- **Extra:** Any additional inversion results a group would like to submit. Please try to change only one aspect at a time compared to the baseline set-up, for ease of analysis.

When submitting the results, please use the following designation to distinguish between the different experiments: base, exp1, exp2, extra.

7. Output Data

To accommodate the analysis of the inversion results, all groups are asked to provide prior and posterior values and uncertainties for different types of output: gridded fluxes, national totals and simulated mole fractions. Please see the sections below for specifications of the desired output.

7.1 Gridded fluxes and uncertainties

Please provide yearly NetCDF4 files with gridded methane fluxes on a 0.25x0.25 degrees spatial grid and monthly resolution, containing:

- Dimensions:
 - latitude [degrees North, center of gridbox, at least 35.125 to 69.875]
 - longitude [degrees East, center of gridbox, at least -14.875 to 34.875]
 - time [day of year]
- Variables [lon x lat x time, kg CH₄ m⁻² h⁻¹, double precision]:
 - prior [prior fluxes]
 - error_prior [prior flux uncertainty]
 - post [optimized fluxes]
 - error_post [uncertainty of optimized fluxes]

Filename format: grid_[yyyy]_[exp]_[model].nc

7.2 National total emissions and uncertainties

In addition to the gridded fluxes we ask you to also provide estimates for the national land-only (so excluding territorial waters) CH₄ emissions and their uncertainties. A country mask (both a high resolution 0.01°x 0.01° mask and a corresponding fractional 0.25°x 0.25° mask are provided) to be used for this aggregation can be downloaded from our Research Drive (see section 10). Please distinguish between the following categories: (fossil fuel) energy use, agriculture and waste, biofuel and biomass burning, wetlands, and other natural emissions. If your set-up does not facilitate separate optimization of these categories you can aggregate the optimized total fluxes according to the prior distribution.

Please provide yearly NetCDF4 files that contain monthly totals for:

- Dimensions:
 - country [name of country, as specified in the country mask]

- month [month number]
- Variables [country x month, Gg CH₄, double precision]:
 - prior_[category]
 - error_prior_[category]
 - post_[category]
 - error_post_[category]
 with *category* denoting: *total, energy, agriwaste, bioburning, wetlands, other*

Filename format: country_[yyyy]_[exp]_[model].nc

7.3 Mixing ratios and uncertainties

Please provide both prior and optimized mixing ratios and the imposed uncertainty for all assimilated observations. Include these results in the provided .csv files, or as a NetCDF4 file with variables:

site, yyyy, mm, dd, hh, mi, ss, yobs, ybkg, ypri, ypos, yerr, (ybkp)

all having the number of observations as dimension. In the above, 'site' represents the 3-character site identifier, 'yobs' the observed value, 'ybkg' the background mixing ratio (use '-999' if not applicable, i.e. for global models), 'ypri' and 'ypos' the prior and posterior mixing ratios respectively, 'yerr' the model-data mismatch used for assimilation (i.e. sum of observation and model uncertainty), and (if applicable) 'ybkp' the optimized background mixing ratio. Report all mixing ratios in ppb.

Filename format: conc_[yyyy]_[exp]_[model].csv/nc

8. Validation

8.1 CH₄ mixing ratios

Some observations are denoted as 'validation' in the site list. Please provide simulated mixing ratios corresponding to these observations (and matching the timestamps) for both the prior and posterior fluxes, using the same format as specified above (use '-999' for 'yerr').

Filename format: val_[yyyy]_[exp]_[model].csv/nc

8.2 Radon mixing ratios

To assess the impact of the performance of the different transport models on national emission estimates we ask you to include radon (²²²Rn) as a tracer for atmospheric transport in your baseline set-up. A climatological flux map of ²²²Rn is provided on our research drive, as constructed by Karstens et al. 2015. Note that we regridded the fluxmap from its original resolution of 0.087°x 0.087° to 0.25°x 0.25°, thereby imposing average flux values per ecosystem type for the cells within our domain that are outside the bounds of the original

map. Please provide hourly simulated concentrations for the year 2018 for the sites indicated in the observations site list, in NetCDF4 files:

- Variables:
 - Time [samples x 6, as [year,month,day,hour,minute,second] for each sample]
 - rn_model [samples, in Bq/m³]

Filename format: rn_[site]_[exp]_[model].nc

9. Documentation

All submissions should be accompanied by a document outlining the inversion set-up(s). This document should include at least:

- Name and email of one contact person
- Name and identifier (used in the filenames) of your inversion system
- Details about the inversion framework:
 - Definition of the state vector
 - Correlation length
 - Optimization method
 - Treatment of background mole fractions (if applicable)
- Details about the transport model:
 - Resolution
 - Name, driving meteorological data, and other relevant settings
 - Estimate for the transport model error as used in the inversion
- Overview of prior emissions and their uncertainties
 - Source (if additional sources are used apart from those listed in section 6.1) and resolution
 - Assumed uncertainty and covariance
- Assimilated observations
 - If you deviated from the provided list, please indicate how and why
- Chi square statistics of the inversion
- Overview of the performed experiments and simulated years.

Filename format: info_[model].txt

10. Logistics

The **deadline for submission of results for phase 1 is March 1, 2022**. We kindly ask potential participants to declare their intention to participate in advance, by sending an email to l.florentie@vu.nl. We encourage modeling groups to participate in both phases of the study, however, this is not a strict requirement.

Input data can be downloaded from our Research Drive. You will be given access after notifying us about your intention to participate.

Your results can be submitted by uploading them to the same Research Drive. Please make sure to keep the filename formats of submitted files as specified above, where [model] represents and identifier for your inversion framework.

For questions and further information, please contact Liesbeth Florentie (l.florentie@vu.nl) or Sander Houweling (s.houweling@vu.nl).

11. Acknowledgements

Thanks to all data providers, in particular to Rona Thompson and Isabelle Pison for harmonizing the observational dataset and input fluxes, and to Arjo Segers for generating the baseline fluxes for Rödenbeck's 2-step inversion approach.

12. References

[1] Karstens, U., Schwingshackl, C., Schmithüsen, D. and Levin, I., *A process-based ²²²radon flux map for Europe and its comparison to long-term observations*, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15, 12845–12865, doi: 10.5194/acp-15-12845-2015, 2015

[2] Petrescu, A.M., Qiu, C., Ciais, P., et al., *The consolidated European synthesis of CH₄ and N₂O emissions for EU27 and UK: 1990-2018*, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 13, 2307-2362, doi: 10.5194/essd-13-2307-2021, 2021

[3] Rödenbeck, C., Gerbig, C., Trusilova, K. and Heimann, M., *A two-step scheme for high-resolution regional atmospheric trace gas inversions based on independent models*, *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.*, 9, 1727–1756, doi: 10.5194/acpd-9-1727-2009, 2009

[4] Saunio, M., Stavert, A.R., Poulter, B., et al., *The global methane budget 2000-2017*, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 1561-623, doi 10.5194/essd-12-1561-2020, 2020

[5] Solazzo, E., Crippa, M., Guizzardi, D., Muntean, M., Choulga, M., Janssens-Maenhout, G., *Uncertainties in the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) emission inventory of greenhouse gases*, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 5655–5683, doi: 10.5194/acp-21-5655-2021, 2021